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Research Article

**MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE PERICARDITIS SUSPENSION AT
FAMILY MEDICINE**

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Article Received: March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

In this review we discuss the background of acute pericarditis, symptoms and treatment are emphasized in order to properly manage this condition. Differentiation diagnosis play important role in case of suspension and elimination the other disease. We conducted a Comprehensive search through electronic databases; Medline, Embase, and Scopus for published articles concerning the acute pericarditis diagnosis, and management in primary care up to January, 2019, using the following search terms: acute pericarditis, primary care, family physicians, diagnosis. Acute pericarditis is inflammation of the pericardium. Acute pericarditis has a number of possible etiologies including infection, acute myocardial infarction, medication usage, trauma to the thoracic dental caries, and systemic ailments, such as rheumatoid arthritis. Nevertheless, most etiologic assessments are inconclusive. Patients with acute pericarditis generally existing with acute, sharp, retrosternal breast discomfort that is relieved by sitting or leaning ahead. A pericardial friction rub is discovered in approximately 85% of patients. Family doctor should be able to differentiate acute pericarditis from other disease, in case patient suspension proper diagnosis with EKG should be done. Classic electrocardiographic modifications include widespread concave upwards ST-segment elevation without reciprocal T-wave inversions or Q waves.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute pericarditis is the most frequent pericardium affliction. It is diagnosed in around 0.1% of patients hospitalized for breast pain and in 5% of patients admitted to the emergency department for chest pain unrelated to acute myocardial infarction (MI) [1]. Although acute pericarditis takes place in all age groups and in men and women, it offers frequently in males 20 to 50 years old [2] Acute pericarditis on its own confers reduced death; however, the high rate of recurrence and the difficulty of regulating signs add to high morbidity. After a first episode of acute pericarditis, 30% of patients have a recurrence [2].

Healthy and balanced pericardium contains the internal serous visceral layer and the external fibrous parietal layer that wrap up the heart. About 15 to 50 mL of fluid, an ultrafiltrate of plasma, divides these layers. Acute pericarditis can result from a systemic ailment or a process isolated to the pericardium [2]. In most immunocompetent patients, viral or idiopathic etiologies are common, but other causes have to be taken into consideration [3]. Localized to the heart, acute pericarditis can happen second to an MI or a studying aortic aneurysm. Systemic conditions, such as malignancy, inflammatory responses, autoimmune conditions (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis), and uremia, can speed up acute pericarditis. Outside reasons besides viral infections include pharmacologic agents (e.g., hydralazine, isoniazid), radiation therapy, blunt or sharp trauma to the thoracic cavity, and bacterial infection [3]. A lot of etiologic evaluations are undetermined.

In this review we discuss the background of acute pericarditis, symptoms and treatment are emphasized

in order to properly manage this condition. Differentiation diagnosis play important role in case of suspension and elimination the other disease.

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted a Comprehensive search through electronic databases; Medline, Embase, and Scopus for published articles concerning the acute pericarditis diagnosis, and management in primary care up to January, 2019, using the following search terms: acute pericarditis, primary care, family physicians, diagnosis. We limited articles extraction in those which were published in English with human subject. bibliographies found in included studies were reviewed for more relevant articles useful for our review.

DISCUSSION:

- **Acute Pericarditis**

Contemporary understanding of acute pericarditis hinges on 3 main factors to consider [4]:

(1) pericarditis occurs in every category of disorder, common and exotic (the spectrum is so broad that with every new situation, the clinician needs to devise an ideal differential medical diagnosis) (Table 1), (2) to stay clear of therapeutic incidents, pericarditis needs to not be misinterpreted for other syndromes, and (3) the etiological and medical spectra of acute pericarditis change regularly and some traditional assumptions and summaries, perpetuated in some publications, are outdated (Table 2) [4], [5]. Except immuno- compromised individuals, specifically in patients with acquired immunodeficiency disorder, there has been a sharp decline in infectious pericarditis [4].

Table 1. Differential Diagnosis for New Acute Cases of Pericardial Disease [5].

1.	Idiopathic pericarditis (specific diagnosis unidentified)
2.	Due to living agents: infectious, parasitic (geographic areas where parasitic disease is common)
3.	Vasculitis-connective tissue disease (38 individual forms)
4.	Immunopathies and/or hypersensitivity states
5.	Diseases of contiguous structures
6.	Disorders of metabolism
7.	Trauma: direct and/or indirect
8.	Neoplasms: primary, metastatic, multicentric
9.	Of uncertain pathogenesis or in association with many syndromes

Table 2. Misconceptions in Pericardial Disease [4], [5], [6].

Pericarditis as a cause of arrhythmias	Acute pericarditis does not create substantial arrhythmias without disorder of the myocardium or valves
Idiopathic pericarditis	Eventually no ailment is idiopathic; term still used when diagnostic researches stop working to establish etiology
Trapezius ridge pain	The trapezius ridges are confused with shoulder and neck by patients and doctors; patients need to be asked to determine pain sites
Pericardial effusions regularly	Many inflammatory effusions have rubs, at least early
PR depression and ST elevation misread due to optical illusion	Electrocardiograms have to be very carefully examined for PR and ST deviations; the TP segment is the electrocardiogram baseline for these
Dangerously reduced coronary blood flow in cardiac tamponade	Coronary blood flow is lowered, however symmetrical to the lowered work of the heart; there is no ischemic contribution from tamponade
Confusion of the role of pulsus paradoxus and Kussmaul sign	Pulsus paradoxus happens in tamponade and in constriction; Kussmaul indication takes place only in restriction, including effusive-constrictive pericarditis
Chronic constrictive pericarditis	Constriction can be acute (list below acute pericarditis by days or weeks), subacute, or chronic; prompt medical diagnosis protects against chronic constriction, currently the least usual kind

- **Clinical Considerations:**

Pericarditis prevails in numerous ailments like rheumatoid arthritis and lupus in which it might or might not appear, or, as during transmural myocardial infarction, generally concealed by various other signs and symptoms. When clinically recognizable, the presentation remains classic: pain throughout the breast but primarily main and generally pleuritic (ie, respirophasic and worse on recumbency) [4]. Nonetheless, pericarditic pain can have all the characteristics of ischemic pain, including the same routes of radiation [5]. A common clinical finding is pain take place- ring in or radiating to one or both trapezius ridges (both phrenic nerves go through the anterior pericardium and innervate each trapezius ridge [4], [5]. Patients that suffer shoulder or neck pain ought to be asked to point to its area to recognize any kind of trapezius ridge involvement.

Suspicion of acute pericarditis necessitates cautious auscultation, particularly the left lower sternal edge and at the cardiac borders. A monophasic, diphasic, or triphasic pericardial rub is diagnostic of acute pericarditis [4], [7]. Although rubs are basically 100% specific, sensitivity depends on regularity of auscultation, because they often tend to come and go over hours. Without a rub, it is difficult at the bedside to be specific regarding acute pericarditis.

Fortuitously, for the most part of common etiologies- idiopathic, autoimmune, or viral (typically clinically

identical)- the very early electrocardiogram (ECG) remains classic (ie, near-ubiquitous ST segment [J point] altitudes), typically with PR segment clinical depressions in a lot of leads and the reverse constantly in a VR and generally V1 (Figure 1). The PR segment inconsistencies might come before ST elevation if the patient is observed not long after the beginning of signs and symptoms [5]. Numerous patients have just PR segment clinical depressions, commonly missed or misunderstood as ST altitudes. Historically, the ECG findings for in a patient with pericarditis progressed from ST elevations (stage 1) with descent of the J points (phase 2) adhered to by T wave inversion (stage 3) to stage 4 (restitution to the baseline ECG) [5], [8]. Today, except for purulent pericarditis, stage 1 alone is regularly the only ECG finding if the patient is without delay dealt with, probably due to effective nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), consisting of aspirin [4]. Although the stage 1 ECG finding is quasi-diagnostic, 43% of patients with rubs providing in the emergency department had an atypical ECG [8]. A common however poorly understood mimic of the stage 1 ECG finding is early repolarization.

In the absence of large controlled clinical trials, anecdotal therapeutic experience needs to be mentioned. Aspirin might be effective, but the best contemporary experience is with ibuprofen¹ and, due to the demonstrated effectiveness of colchicine (as monotherapy or combined treatment), the best mix

may be advil, 800 mg every 8 hours, and colchicine, 0.6 mg twice everyday [9]. Colchicine likewise often tends to stop reoccurring pericarditis. Ibuprofen has the advantage of fairly couple of adverse results and the possible advantage of enhancing coronary flow. In contrast, indomethacin usually controls pain but has a bad negative effect pro- file and minimizes coronary flow [10]. (No trials of cyclooxygenase 2 inhibitors for pericarditis are offered.) Although controlled tests are lacking, incorporated therapy normally is adequate within 1 to 3 days. Incorporated therapy could be proceeded for 7 to 14 days complied with by tapering for an additional 1 or 2 weeks because of the

opportunity of early recurrence. An oral corticosteroid needs to just be made use of if it is likewise indicated for an underlying disease or if the patient's syndrome is severe and immune to NSAIDs [4]. It shows up that the very early use of corticosteroids in a lot of forms of pericarditis actually adds to reappearance, frequently a stubborn, corticosteroid-dependent, and disabling syndrome [9]. Many patients do not want to be physically active throughout an acute strike, and physical activity might intensify accompanying superficial myocarditis; undoubtedly, classic ST-T segment adjustments mirror myocarditis [4], [5].

Figure 1. Classic Stage 1 Electrocardiogram, Quasi-diagnostic for Acute Pericarditis.

Near-ubiquitous J-point and ST elevations; J-point depressions in aVR and V1. Near-ubiquitous PR segment depressions; PR elevations in aVR.

- **Confusion With Other Disease:**

The most typical complex element in the medical diagnosis of acute pericarditis is ECG misconception, especially as acute myocardial infarction. The differential medical diagnosis is summed up in Table 3. Computers are prone to diagnose infarction, generally inferolateral, which is especially misleading in patients with nonpleuritic chest region pain. This has brought about thrombolysis without coronary damage, in some cases triggering pericardial hemorrhage and tamponade. For unidentified factors, this is unusual with warfarin anticoagulation. Differential medical diagnosis might end up being harder, since serum enzyme and troponin degrees normally rise [4]. These show the superficial myocarditis with creatine phosphokinase of muscle

band and troponin levels roughly paralleling the degree of ST elevation. These levels are not yet examined in epistenocardiac pericarditis- pericarditis early during myocardial infarction [9]. In practice, complication with pulmonary syndromes consisting of pleurisy, mostly because of respirophasic pain, is rarely a problem. Sometimes pulmonary embolism signs recommend pericardial ailment, rarely with a pulmonary Dressler syndrome (clinically completely dry or effusive pericarditis adhering to pulmonary embolism) [4], [5]. The discomfort of dissecting aortic hematoma might not only simulate pericarditis, however dissecting blood may go into the pericardium generating rubs and suggestive ECG abnormalities [5]. Echocardiography or computed tomography normally determines the aortic lesion.

Table 3. Acute Pericarditis vs Acute Ischemia ^[5].

	Acute Pericarditis	Acute Ischemia
Characteristics of Pain		
Onset	More often sudden	Usually gradual, crescendo
Main location	Substernal or left precordial	Same as pericarditis or confined to zones of radiation
Radiation	May be same as ischemic; trapezius ridge(s) common	Shoulders, arms, neck, jaw back; not trapezius ridge(s)
Quality	Usually sharp, stabbing; background ache or dull and oppressive	Usually heavy (pressure sensation) or burning
Inspiration	Worse	No effect unless associated with peri-infarction pericarditis
Duration	Persistent; may wax and wane	Usually intermittent; <30 minutes each recurrence, longer for unstable angina
Ordinary movements body	Increased	Usually no effect
Posture	Worse on recumbency; improved on sitting, leaning forward	No effect or improvement on sitting
Nitrates	No effect	Usually relief
Clinical Factors		
Myocardial enzymes	Normal or elevated	Elevated (infarct)
Pericardial friction	Rub (most cases)	Rub only if with infarction pericarditis
S3	Absent unless preexisting	May be present
S4	Absent unless preexisting	Nearly always present
S1	Intact	Often dull, not distinct, after first day
Pulmonary congestion	Absent	May be present
Murmurs	Absent unless preexisting	May be present
Electrocardiogram Findings		
J-ST	Diffuse elevation; usually concave, without reciprocal depressions	Localized deviation; usually convex (with reciprocals in infarction)
PR segment depression	Frequent	Rare
Abnormal Q waves	None unless with infarction	Common with infarction (Q wave infarcts)
T waves	Inverted after J points return to baseline	Inverted while J-ST still elevated (infarct)
Arrhythmia	None in absence of heart disease	Frequent
Conduction abnormalities	None in absence of heart disease	Frequent

- **Treatment:**

Several patients with pericarditis can be efficiently dealt with in the outpatient setting. Clinical presentation, presumed etiology, medical history, and feedback to previous therapies assist determine management alternatives. Patients at greater risk ought to be dealt with in the healthcare facility [11].

- **NSAIDs:**

Although there are no randomized controlled trials to date, pericarditis generally is dealt with empirically with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [12]. Patients with assumed viral or idiopathic pericarditis must begin on NSAIDs and proceed up until signs and symptom resolution, which generally

takes two weeks [14]. Although various NSAIDs are offered, there is no proof that any specific one is superior to another for treating acute pericarditis. Nonetheless, the preferred agent to treat acute pericarditis triggered by MI is aspirin in a dose of 650 to 1,000 mg 4 times per day with a taper over 4 weeks [12], [13].

An empirical research with aspirin (800 mg by mouth every 6 to eight hours for 7 to 10 days followed by a 2- to three-week taper) and gastroprotection revealed a resolution rate of 87% with follow-up for 38 months [13]. Ibuprofen, which may be liked due to the damaging impact profile, can be prescribed at 300 to 800 mg every 6 to 8 hours tapered to 800 mg weekly over 3 to 4 weeks [11], [12]. Indomethacin (Indocin) must be suggested at 75 to 150 mg day-to-day [11]. Tapering will certainly lower the risk of recurrences and need to be guided by signs and symptoms and inflammatory markers (e.g., erythrocyte sedimentation rate, CRP degree) [14]. Patients must restrict strenuous tasks till they are discomfort free and their biomarkers have normalized [14]. Gastroprotection must be made use of in appropriate patients while they are taking NSAIDs.

Colchicine:

Colchicine is used to deal with frequent pericarditis or pericarditis that does not reply to standard therapy [15]. European guidelines also recommend colchicine as a feasible initial treatment option for acute pericarditis [12]. In one possible, randomized, open-label study, patients with acute pericarditis obtained traditional treatment plus colchicine or standard therapy alone. Patients who received colchicine had a substantially lower reoccurrence rate at 18 months (10.7% vs. 32.3%; $P = .004$) and symptom determination at 72 hours (11.7% vs. 36.7%; $P = .003$) [16]. When combined with an NSAID, colchicine reduced symptoms, lowered rate of recurrence, and was far better tolerated than an NSAID alone.

These findings were validated in a subsequent multicenter, randomized, double-blind, regulated test in which colchicine or placebo was contributed to standard treatment in patients with acute pericarditis. Colchicine was given at a dosage of 0.5 mg twice daily for three months in patients weighing more than 154 lb (70 kg) or 0.5 mg once daily in patients weighing 154 lb or less. Incessant or recurring pericarditis occurred in 16.7% of the colchicine group vs. 37.5% of the placebo group (relative risk = 0.56; 95% confidence period, 0.30 to 0.72; number required to deal with = 4; $P < .001$). Colchicine also decreased the rate of sign determination at 72 hours (19.2% vs. 40%;

$P = .001$), minimized the number of reappearances per patient (0.21 vs. 0.52; $P = .001$), and boosted the remission rate at one week (85% vs. 58.3%; $P < .001$) [15].

Colchicine ought to not be taken with macrolides and ought to be made use of meticulously in patients with kidney insufficiency because colchicine levels will enhance. Upkeep or prophylactic dosages of colchicine ought to be minimized by 50% in patients older than 70 years that have impaired kidney function and glomerular purification rates less than 50 mL per minute [11]. Additional possible adverse results include diarrhea (up to 10% of cases), nausea, vomiting, myotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and bone marrow suppression [11]. Standard blood evaluation (including complete blood count, and transaminase, creatine kinase, and serum creatinine levels) need to be carried out at the time of colchicine initiation and approximately one month later on to assess for damaging results [11].

Glucocorticoids:

Glucocorticoids should not be utilized as first-line treatment for patients with acute pericarditis. Glucocorticoid usage during acute pericarditis confers a significant threat of damaging results and feasible recurrence of pericarditis (odds ratio = 4.30; 95% confidence interval, 1.21 to 15.25; $P = .024$) triggered by reactivation of a viral infection or a boost in viral duplication [11]. Nonetheless, glucocorticoids might be thought about when the root cause of the acute pericarditis is connective tissue illness, autoreactivity, or uremia [12]. Prednisone might be suggested at 1 mg per kg per day with a rapid taper or titrated to a dose that achieves clinical benefit (0.25 mg per kg per day). Towards the end of the taper (usually 6 to 8 weeks), NSAIDs or colchicine can be introduced to reduce the risk of reappearance [11]. The taper is based upon medical symptoms and serum biomarkers. If symptoms return, NSAIDs can be included. If symptoms do not enhance, the last dosage of glucocorticoids that suppressed signs and symptoms should be rebooted. Glucocorticoid treatment should be proceeded for 2 to 3 weeks [11]. Consultation with a cardiologist is suggested for patients with severe illness, those with pericarditis refractory to treatment, and those with unclear etiologies.

CONCLUSION:

Acute pericarditis is inflammation of the pericardium. Acute pericarditis has a number of possible etiologies including infection, acute myocardial infarction, medication usage, trauma to the thoracic dental caries, and systemic ailments, such as rheumatoid arthritis.

Nevertheless, most etiologic assessments are inconclusive. Patients with acute pericarditis generally existing with acute, sharp, retrosternal breast discomfort that is relieved by sitting or leaning ahead. A pericardial friction rub is discovered in approximately 85% of patients. Family doctor should be able to differentiate acute pericarditis from other disease, in case patient suspension proper diagnosis with EKG should be done. Classic electrocardiographic modifications include widespread concave upwards ST-segment elevation without reciprocal T-wave inversions or Q waves. This condition can be treated efficiently in outpatient. Treatment for acute pericarditis should be focused on the underlying etiology and the absence or presence of other underlying disease. It is constantly medically important to omit underlying microbial infection, systemic illness and malignancy. In the presence of systemic disease suitable therapy for underlying etiology needs to be applied. Also, epidemiological background (especially high or low tuberculosis prevalence) should be taken into consideration. First-line treatment includes nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and colchicine. Glucocorticoids are commonly booked for extreme or refractory situations, or in cases when the source of pericarditis is likely connective tissue illness, autoreactivity, or uremia. Cardiology appointment is recommended for patients with severe illness, those with pericarditis refractory to empiric therapy, and those with uncertain etiologies.

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